

ASSESSMENT OF FIRE DAMAGE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS FROM SURFACE FEATURES

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ABSTRACT

There is a high possibility that composite structures may be subjected to fire. Hence, the study on the response of composites to fire and the development of a non-destructive evaluation method to assess the damage become very important. In this research, an attempt has been made to establish a correlation between the fire damaged composite surface features and the stiffness degradation. Digital imaging techniques were employed to determine the surface features. The stiffness of the fire damaged composite panels were determined by three point bending test. The results indicate a good correlation between the surface features and the stiffness degradation.

Keywords: composites, fire damage, image analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

When a composite structure or component is damaged by fire, a decision regarding whether to replace or repair the damaged component should be made. Hence the strength degradation of the composite material must be assessed by non-destructive means. To this end, a non-destructive evaluation is required to assess the damage, based on the surface features of the fire damaged composites. In practical applications, especially in aircraft and military applications, it is desired that the damage due to fire be assessed quickly and by simple means.

Digital imaging technique is an important tool in non-destructive evaluation that can meet these requirements. Since digital images can be acquired and analyzed by a computer, the speed of the damage assessment system will be significantly higher than conventional methods. Complete automation is also possible using an imaging system. A typical imaging system consists of a CCD camera, a frame grabber, a monitor and a host computer.

When a composite panel is exposed to flame normal to its surface, the flame spreads concentrically on the composite panel surface. Hence the temperature to which the panel is exposed varies radially from the center of the exposed area. The severity of damage is proportional to the exposure temperature. Hence the severity of damage also varies concentrically, resulting in concentric rings. These rings are visible on the surface of the composite panel and represent

different levels of damage. Since the temperature distribution is continuous on the surface of the panel, the different areas may not be distinctly separated but with a small transition zone. In practice, due to the wavy, unsteady nature of the flame tip, the rings may not be exactly circular.

The main objective of this research was to determine the possibility of a correlation between surface features and stiffness degradation of a fire-damaged composite. Imaging techniques were employed to determine the surface features of the damaged composite surface. Basically, an attempt has been made to determine whether a correlation exists between the stiffness degradation and the surface features. Also the possibility of using imaging techniques to determine the surface features has been validated.

1.1. Fire Damage on Composites

A very limited amount of information is available on the effect of fire on composites. Although a significant amount of research has been carried out in the US Air Force and Navy, many of the works have not been released to the public.

Several researchers have studied the effect of environmental changes such as temperature, moisture etc on composite materials. Springer [1,2,3] conducted several investigations on the moisture and temperature induced degradation of composites, especially graphite epoxy composites. An analytical model for predicting the mechanical properties of composites at elevated temperatures has been developed [4].

Griffis et al. [5] studied the thermal response of graphite-epoxy composites subjected to rapid heating. They developed a simplified one-dimensional model for transient heat transfer analysis of composites exposed to surface heating. This model was verified with the experimental results obtained by exposing graphite epoxy laminate to laser irradiation.

Degradation of tensile and shear properties of composites, when exposed to fire, was studied by Pering et al. [6]. A correlation was established between the degradation of mechanical properties and the calculated mass loss and the char layer thickness. This correlation was found to be valid only up to the point of delamination.

1.2. Application of Imaging Techniques

Because of its numerous advantages, imaging techniques have been employed in many applications such as robotics, remote sensing and medical applications. Optical imaging techniques have also been applied to composite materials. Russell et al. [7] quantitatively evaluated the impact and fabrication damage on a glass fiber reinforced composite system using image correlation techniques. Two speckle images, before and after loading, were compared by a computer image identification algorithm to compute the displacement and strain field. Anomalies present in the strain field were used to locate regions of suspected damage and also to quantify the severity of damage.

Imaging techniques have been applied in fiber angle orientation analysis of graphite/epoxy composites [8]. In this research, the unclear boundary between fiber and matrix was identified manually and an artificial, distinct boundary was incorporated back into the frame memory using image analysis software. The artificial boundary was used in the data analysis.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental setup used in this research included a fire chamber for exposing the composites to flame, an imaging system for acquiring and analyzing the images of damaged composite surface and a mechanical testing system for determining the stiffness.

2.1. Fire Chamber

The major components of the fire chamber are an oxy-acetylene torch, a torch holder, a panel holder and a door. The torch is secured to a holder which can slide freely inside the chamber walls. The panel is fitted to a holder, which slides between two brackets perpendicular to the torch. By varying the distance between the nozzle and the panel, the area of exposure and the exposure temperature can be controlled.

Two type K thermocouples were used, one for measuring the flame temperature at the center of the panel and another 50mm away from the center. The thermocouples were connected to a pre-calibrated and computerized data acquisition system, from which the output could be read directly.

2.2. Imaging System

The schematic of the imaging system setup is shown in Figure 1. This consists of a CCD (Charge Coupled Device) color camera for viewing the specimen, a color monitor for displaying images and two boards, color frame grabber (CFG) and VISIONplus-AT image processing accelerator (VIPA). These two boards are plugged directly into the expansion slots of the host Computer. Image analysis modules were developed for measurement of area and gray level of damage regions.

Figure 1. Schematic of digital imaging system

2.3. Mechanical Testing System

The system corporation's 810 Material Testing System (MTS) was used for testing the specimen. The data obtained were the stroke of the loading roller and the corresponding load, as well as the maximum stroke and the failure load. The test results were obtained directly from a Measurement Group, Inc.'s computerized Data Acquisition System 400 and stored on a floppy diskette.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The specimen under investigation was ICI T300/394 24 ply unidirectional graphite/epoxy composite laminate. The nominal size of the specimen was 180mm by 230mm and approximately 3mm thick.

3.1. Acquisition of Images

The damaged composite surface was viewed through the CCD camera and digitized by CFG. This image was viewed on the special color monitor. Before storing the image, the image had to be calibrated. A square grid of side 254mm was used for this purpose. This square was placed in front of the damaged panel and viewed in the monitor. Then the number of pixels required to represent 254mm along both X and Y axes could be determined. This information was used to determine the actual area represented by each pixel.

3.2. Mechanical Testing

The bending test specimen was prepared from the damaged panel by cutting it into a number of strips of width 25mm. The strips were cut along the direction of fiber. Each strip had different area of various damage regions. The central strip had all the damage level regions, whereas the outermost strip was fully undamaged.

The strips were subjected to three point bending test in the Material Testing System. The specimen was deflected at a rate of 2.5mm/minute. The displacement at the center of the strip and the corresponding load were recorded at suitable intervals. The measurements were taken up to the point of failure. The deflection and load data were recorded at regular intervals of load. From the load-deflection data, the stiffness of the strip was determined.

3.3. Damaged Surface Feature Extraction

The image of the damaged composite surface was first subjected to contrast stretching, which is an image enhancement operation. The two important surface features measured were the areas and gray level values of different damage regions. The area of damage regions was determined for each strip in a panel whereas the average gray level of damage regions was determined once for each panel. Figure 2 shows an image of the composite surface with boundaries drawn.

Figure 2. Enhanced digital image of composite panel with boundary contours

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental results obtained in this research can be classified under two groups, namely, mechanical testing and image analysis. The results from mechanical testing and image analysis of various fire damaged panels were reduced for further analysis and comparison. The correlation of damaged surface features with the strength degradation involved two steps. Firstly, the surface features of each damaged panel were correlated with the stiffness degradation determined by the three point bending test. Then in the second step, an attempt was made to check if any general relationship could be established between different panels for stiffness degradation estimation based on the surface features. In this research, the average gray level of the damaged areas were used for characterizing the extent of damage.

4.1. Stiffness Degradation in a Panel

The data obtained from the three point bending test were the deflection of the strip at the center and the corresponding load. From these data, the stiffness of each strip was calculated. When a composite panel is exposed to flame, its stiffness varies with respect to the temperature and the duration of exposure. Since the flame spreads over the panel surface, the exposure temperature of the panel actually varies over the surface. Hence the damage level of each strip cut from the panel also varies. The strip containing the center of exposure should have more variation in stiffness than the adjacent strips. It was found that even if the panel was exposed for a brief period, it developed concentric rings even before actual burning. The results indicated that the stiffness actually increased in case of panels exposed for shorter periods of time. This increase in the stiffness is due to the effect called thermal quenching. Only the burnt panel showed reduction in stiffness.

In all the tests, third strip is the one which carried the largest portion of the damage areas, i.e. it was obtained from the center of the concentric rings. Hence, the variation in the stiffness is maximum in the third strip and decreases gradually on either side of it. It can also be noted from

the result that the overall stiffness of the strip increases with respect to the duration of exposure. This holds good only up to the point of combustion or burning of the composite panel. Once the panel starts burning, the stiffness decreases very rapidly with respect to duration of exposure.

4.2. Image Analysis of Damaged Composite Surfaces

The images of damaged composite surfaces were enhanced and analyzed for the determination of area and average gray level of different damage regions. Even though the damage profile may not be discrete over the specimen surface, two distinct damage regions could be identified on all the composite surfaces. The identification of different damage regions was done by manual inspection based mainly on the gray level difference.

4.3. Relationship Between Damage Area and Stiffness

In order to generalize the study and comparison of test results for different panels, area ratios were determined. This eliminated the need for scaling due to the difference in the magnification of images. Area ratio of a damage region refers to the ratio of area of that damage region to that of the whole strip between the two supports in the bending test. Plots comparing the stiffness degradation in a panel and the corresponding damage area ratios were then prepared.

Figure 3 shows a typical relationship between the area ratios and the stiffness of a strip within a panel. The area ratio AR1 refers to the damage region in the center of the damage whereas AR2 refers to the adjacent damage region away from the center. Due to the difference in the nature of flame reaching the panel which depends on the distance between the nozzle and the panel, the severity of damage differs between the damage regions. It can be seen from this figure that AR1 and stiffness are inversely related. But AR2 does not seem to have a significant effect on the stiffness as it follows a pattern of variation different from that of the stiffness.

Figure 3. Stiffness and area ratios for composite panel strips

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this research, imaging techniques have been applied to extract and measure the surface features of the damaged composite. The image processing techniques were particularly helpful in the enhancement of the various damage regions. The contrast stretching technique was utilized to distinctly identify different damage regions. Also the gray level ratio determined using the image analysis techniques was useful in the characterization of various degrees of damage. Apart from this, once the different damage regions were identified, the areas were determined relatively easier and quicker. An automatic damage area assessment, if developed, can improve the speed to a greater extent. From these advantages of imaging techniques, it can be concluded that image processing technique is a powerful tool that can be effectively used in the estimation of property degradation of flame damaged composites.

Acknowledgements

This project was sponsored by the Material Technology Center of Southern Illinois University at Carbondale. The authors wish to thank Dr. Morris Wright, Director of MTC, for his support and encouragement.

References

1. Springer, G. S., *Moisture and Temperature Induced Degradation of Graphite Epoxy Composites*, Environmental Effects on Composite Materials, Vol. 2, pp. 6-19, Technomic Publishing Company, Inc., 1981,
2. Springer, G. S., and Tsai, S. W., *Thermal Conductivities of Unidirectional Materials*, Environmental Effects on Composite Materials, Vol. 1, pp. 7-15, Technomic Publishing Company, Inc., 1981.
3. Shen, C. H., and Springer, G. S., *Effects of Moisture and Temperature on the Tensile Strength of Composite Materials*, Environmental Effects on Composite Materials, Vol. 1, pp. 79-94, Technomic Publishing Company, Inc., 1981.
4. Springer, G. S., *Model for Predicting the Mechanical Properties of Composites at Elevated Temperatures*, Environmental Effects on Composite Materials, Vol. 2, pp. 151-161, Technomic Publishing Company, Inc., 1984.
5. Griffis, C. A., Masumura, R. A., and Chang, C. I., *Thermal Response of Graphite Epoxy Composite Subjected to Rapid Heating*, Environmental Effects on Composite Materials, Vol. 2, pp. 245-260, Technomic Publishing Company, Inc., 1984.
6. Pering, G. A., Farrell, P. V., and Springer, G. S., *Degradation of Tensile and Shear Properties of Composites Exposed to Fire or Elevated Temperature*, Environmental Effects on Composite Materials, Vol. 1, pp. 145-158, Technomic Publishing Company, Inc., 1981.
7. Russell, M. A., Sutton, M. A., and Chen, H. S., *Image Correlation Quantitative Nondestructive Evaluation of Impact and Fabrication Damage in a Glass Fiber-Reinforced Composite System*, Materials Evaluation, Vol. 47, pp. 550-557, May 1989.
8. Yen, S. C., Chu, T. C., and Jao, H., *Applications of Optical Microscopic Image Analysis to Composite Materials*, Experimental Techniques, Vol. 15, No. 5, pp. 22-25, May 1991.